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Entrepreneurship Education Ecosystems in Engineering and Technology (E4T)

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INTRODUCTION

Vibrant entrepreneurship ecosystems have developed within the CLUSTER Consortium (www.cluster.org) universities with significant contributions to European and global startups and entrepreneurial initiatives. CLUSTER is a consortium of 12 top engineering and technology universities in Europe and 6 top-level associated members from other continents. A subset of the CLUSTER members is involved in the E4T (Entrepreneurship Education Ecosystems in Engineering and Technology) Erasmus+ Strategic Partnership project (2017-1-SE01-KA203-034536) which develops interactive programs for our students to participate in piloting and co-creation of a joint program ingrained within these ecosystems.

The overall aim of the study is to provide more graduates in engineering with entrepreneurial ambition, culture and skills, and to draw on the entrepreneurial ecosystems as a platform for inspiration, as follows: 1) Develop models for

ingraining entrepreneurship education into specific engineering and technology M.Sc. curricula at the partner universities; 2) Drive new course concepts into the policy actions of the partnering universities at the level of the Faculty/Dean/Programme director/individual teacher; 3) Build a network for Entrepreneurship education by implementing a pilot between the CLUSTER Universities within their innovation and entrepreneurial ecosystems; 4) Share best practices for promoting hands-on-entrepreneurial skills within accelerators, local hubs, technology platform and student - driven start-up activities; 5) Piloting of the educational ecosystem network in collaboration with a dynamic set of stakeholders including academic institutions, companies, local, regional and national agencies and most importantly our students as co-creators of their education, 6) Create university-level and transnational training programs for teachers and professors to integrate elements promoting the development of entrepreneurial skills via specific engineering/technology/ science disciplines.

1. BACKGROUND

Universities, education systems and societies are undergoing major structural changes, and future employment of graduates calls for innovative integration of entrepreneurship into their disciplinary knowledge and skills. The Cluster Consortium has responded to the multidisciplinary challenges of future education by building entrepreneurship ecosystems which can support the development of entrepreneurial skills. However, there is not one unique method by which entrepreneurship skills can become integrated into education, rather it is important to recognize that the fundamental challenge is ingraining and embedding entrepreneurial educational contents into the major and minor specific courses that the students pursue.

It is important to recognize that entrepreneurship per se can be viewed as a specific discipline, eg. in business schools, however, in engineering and technology, the core of the educational outcome is based on a strong disciplinary knowledge in technology, engineering and science. Namely, a student in chemical engineering, electrical engineering, mechanical engineering etc. must acquire an understanding of entrepreneurial approaches through a strong foundation in the future applications in chemistry/automation/ mechatronics etc. This foundation, when embedded into an entrepreneurial mindset is the basis for fueling the emergence of innovations. Accordingly, at Cluster universities the aim is to enable each student to become engaged in the respective entrepreneurship ecosystems and to develop an entrepreneurial mindset. The extent to which a student adopts such working skills, will vary. Some may end up as experts of in-house entrepreneurship within companies and industry, some as interlocutors between the needs of society and agencies for delivery of hands-on outcomes of emerging innovations, and some may found a start –up and becoming an entrepreneur. Such skills, adopted by graduates, are a crucial driver for future European economy and welfare.

For universities of technology, engineering and science this poses a specific demand as it is not sufficient to link entrepreneurship studies to content and delivery of education. Rather, content and delivery of disciplinary studies must serve as enablers of development of entrepreneurial skills for future graduates.

The overall objective of the present study is therefore to provide more graduates in engineering with entrepreneurial ambition, culture and skills (eg. proof of concepts phase for startups).

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The specific objectives of E4T are to:

1) Develop models for ingraining entrepreneurship education into specific engineering and technology curricula at the M.Sc. level at the different partner universities. This should happen by embedding and ingraining entrepreneurial skills into the disciplinary studies of students at technical universities. This process will also aim to change the traditional view of top University Management about the delivery of discipline-specific teaching to support teachers in their quest to integrate entrepreneurial skills into engineering/technology/science courses. This should lead to drive new course concepts into the policy actions of the partnering universities at the level of the Faculty/Dean/Programme director/individual teacher.

2) Create university-level and transnational training programs for teachers (professors/academic staff/lecturers) to integrate elements promoting the development of entrepreneurial skills via specific engineering/technology/science related disciplines. This will be achieved by developing learning and coaching methods, tools for providing feedback, and how to manage group dynamics and approaches to assessment of development of skills via feedback from students and stakeholders. Teachers who are interested in integrating entrepreneurship will be provided with approaches into their specific engineering/science /technology courses with clear instructions for the amount of time, resources, student and teacher work, spaces etc. that the teacher and the university should take into account when planning and executing these courses. These quantitative estimates of workload, time and teacher /student input are also used to engage program leaders/deans to adopt such courses into the curriculum, as they will require special arrangements and do differ from traditional curriculum design. By collaborating in the transnational setting, the teachers can support the development of student worldviews, as a key to global entrepreneurship and in cooperation with national, regional and local stakeholders of the participating partner universities.

3) Build a network for Entrepreneurship education by implementing a pilot between the Cluster Universities within their entrepreneurial ecosystems. The partners will in this way share best practices for promoting hands-on-entrepreneurial skills within accelerators, local hubs, technology platform and student - driven start-up activities.

Each ecosystem in which entrepreneurial skills develop is part of dynamic processes that are influenced by local and regional stakeholders, which vary from country to country and location to location. Education in these ecosystems is influenced by a dynamic set of stakeholders including academic institutions, companies, local, regional and national agencies, with the values and ethics of society and culture adding a specific flavor to the ecosystem, which will all be taken into account and analyzed to collect and share good practices.

The main final expected tangible results at the end of E4T lifetime can therefore be summarized as follows:

- A constantly updated report on the state of the art for what concerns the existing entrepreneurship and innovation ecosystems at the partner universities, best practices inside and outside of the consortium and status at technical universities for the introduction of elements of entrepreneurship education in their curricular and extra-curricular activities;
- Articles on Entrepreneurship Education as a result of the carried out activities presenting some recent and relevant analyses based on case studies of technical universities in Europe;

- Success stories/Case studies to be made permanently available on E4T website as well as videos and written testimonials;
- A consolidated programme on entrepreneurship for engineering studies running every year with the support of private sponsors;
- Online facilitation tools to support the trainers in delivering the above mentioned programme and to introduce entrepreneurship education in the curricular activities;
- A number of start-ups created by the graduates attending the programme and working in teams;
- A number of international entrepreneurs profiles active in the labour market;
- A permanent network of universities aiming at promoting entrepreneurship elements in technical studies.

3. COMPLETED STEPS

The first two steps of the study have been completed in April 2018 and the remaining actions are currently being defined under the “Development” phase and will be finalized in June 2018 when the course will be launched.

3.1 State of the Art

The first step in the study focused on a report on best practices and repository on the integration of entrepreneurship education in the curricular and extra-curricular activities of technical universities. E4T has covered both best practices identified within the consortium and at other leading universities around the world in terms of programmes in place, objectives, target groups, teaching methodologies, barriers to the introduction of entrepreneurship education in the curricular activities of technical universities. Such an extensive report with a transnational perspective was so far not available and the same goes for the repository of best practices in entrepreneurship education.

Regarding entrepreneurship education in the curricular and extra-curricular activities, the review showed that all studied Cluster universities have substantial activities ongoing. For example all universities had both accelerators and co-working spaces dedicated to supporting entrepreneurial activities. Some notable examples include the pre-incubator at KTH that aim to support the commercialization of ideas from researchers and students: KTH Innovation. This pre-incubator functions as the main gateway to the university’s innovation support system, which has several incubators and co-working space. KTH Innovation receives ideas from individuals and supports their development, often by linking an initial technical solution to potential target markets and suitable business models. The ideas are evaluated in a systematic process, and supported until it becomes possible to start work on realizing it. They also to some extent educate the founding team with basic entrepreneurial tools. If the idea remains promising, or can be developed into a pursuable start-up, it gets channeled to the main incubator STING (Stockholm Innovation and Growth), or to accelerators at the EIT hubs, or other affiliated entities in the Stockholm startup ecosystem. In total there are more than 13 different entities available in this diverse and loosely connected system, functioning as a nurturing living network of nodes for unplanned interaction, idea exchange, and specific technical specialization.

Other universities, for example Darmstadt Technical University and KU Leuven, appear to have a more integrative approach, converging activities to a central place with capabilities to support cross-discipline interaction. One example is the “Home of

Innovation, Growth, Entrepreneurship and Technology Management” (HIGHEST) portfolio of initiatives at DTU. It includes seTUp-Programm, a 6 months accelerator program, HIGHEST-Summer School (for TU students), workshops by the HIGHEST-Buddies (e.g. pitch-training, design thinking, agile teamwork), and a bi-monthly Founders table. Founders can also get individual coaching, consulting and workshops from HIGHEST Startup consultants. At KU Leuven, the “Leuven Community for Innovation and Entrepreneurship” (Lcie) functions as a one-stop shop for students, researchers, professors and alumni. Lcie connects entrepreneurially minded individuals to stimulate, encourage and support entrepreneurship. Its goal is to foster entrepreneurship at the university, thereby acting as a change agent in embedding entrepreneurship into the curriculum where deemed useful. Lcie plays as coordinator of initiatives, support for activities, and provides coaching tailored to individual needs. More than 400 students in almost 100 teams have received coaching so far. The resulting startups have raised more than 9 million euro of capital and employ more than 75 people. Lcie is now being consolidated and seeks an appropriate governance structure to embed the initiative.

In total, there is currently at least 33 accelerators and 26 co-coworking spaces at the 8 investigated universities, including Kiuas, TeamUp, and StartUpSauna at Aalto University, SSES and STING at KTH, IstartLab at IST Lisbon, Tangent at Trinity, LRD at KU Leuven, I3P, Treatbit and Click at Politecnico, and the European Innovation Academy (EIA). There is considerable heterogeneity among these initiatives in terms of organization, tech-transfer focus, degree of field specialization, openness to the society in general (e.g. collaborations with companies), and collaborations with incubators and venture capital organizations. Most universities report challenges in coordinating all these activities and that the support from university government bodies is fundamental. In addition to these initiatives, all universities also give courses in entrepreneurship and innovation and most have course offerings for all levels of study. However, even though there is a great interest for these courses, many universities face difficulties making them available to the broad population of students, as they have to compete with many other courses for those rare electable credits in the programs.

The international benchmark is still ongoing. Tentative findings include that many of the successful universities appear to have a central entity nurturing entrepreneurial competence and activity that coordinates teaching and support (eg. HEC, TU/e, EPFL, Stanford). Some, but not all, also integrate entrepreneurship research into these units. Occurring at several locations is the approach to have students working on projects in cross-disciplinary teams. In some cases individuals compete to make the team select their business idea, but in others they are given a challenge from a company or a community entity (eg McMaster University). These challenge-driven programs appear to have a large personal impact on those involved, including a feeling of contribution to solving an important problem. An example is the Innovation for Change (I4C) programme, by the Politecnico di Torino, SAFM (Scuola di Alta Formazione al Management) and CERN. I4C is a competition between multi-disciplinary teams that aims to find an innovative solution to some global issue. Eight teams of MBA students of SAFM and PhD students of the Politecnico di Torino work in Geneva and Turin for five months between training sessions and group work. The project involve collaboration with several institutions and companies, exposing the students the challenges on which to focus their efforts to find practical solutions. The teams work with global challenges based on the 17 United Nation Goals for sustainable development. They are supported by SAFM alumni, who have become entrepreneurs or work in large industrial groups, as well as by researchers at CERN

and Politecnico. In their work they can use tools and advanced technology solutions up to the realization of prototypes. IdeaSquare, the experimental structure of CERN dedicated to projects of research and development and interdisciplinary programs, is at the students' disposal to work on these projects. Regarding barriers and challenges to ingraining entrepreneurship into curricular and non-curricular activities, the most important appear to be the resistance to change, both from the administration and from conservative faculty members. Considerable bureaucracy tends to slow down progress of integrating entrepreneurship. It is also often hard to make entrepreneurship a priority for the technical faculty, as their own field tends to come first. It is therefore important to design initiatives to be resilient and focus on the long-term impact. In many cases it has taken more than five years to build the activities that now are strong models to follow. To some degree, it is possible to overcome resistance by acting entrepreneurially and by putting some initiatives outside the university bureaucracy. These can then support the efforts as show-cases of success.

3.2 Creating Awareness

The second work package focused on creating awareness and motivation (students at an early stage, teachers, Deans, Programme Directors, university management) about the advantages and importance of entrepreneurship for engineering students and make the process viable (marketing and sales activities approach) through a bottom up approach. Indeed, Souitaris et al., (2007) show that entrepreneurship courses raise some attitudes and the overall entrepreneurial intention and that inspiration (a construct with an emotional element) of science and engineering students.

Structure of the WP:

- a. Choose success cases/stories
- b. Case descriptions with video and short text
- c. Event format for promoting
- d. CLUSTER symposium in November 2017 can be part of this WP

Dissemination of Best Practices will continue throughout the E4T-project as the goal is to produce novel content on entrepreneurship education ecosystems in the context of engineering. Furthermore, we are working on developing a showcase where an assessment method is developed for analyzing the learning outcomes of entrepreneurship education practices.

The goals of the dissemination in the present study is to raise awareness on entrepreneurial education and to share tools to support the development of flexible models for entrepreneurship education ingrained into our ecosystems. Moreover, we aim increase the availability and easy access of different ways of acquiring knowledge and working life skills through development of an entrepreneurial mindset. Accordingly, our target groups for dissemination are stakeholders of academic education: students, teachers, program leaders as well as support and management of teaching development (Table 1).

Table 1. Aims and outcomes for target groups

Aims	Students	Teachers	Teaching Development and Management

Increasing awareness of the available entrepreneurship education	Increased awareness of courses, accelerators, spaces available at E4T universities offered for the targeted student groups / courses	Building a network between the entrepreneurship ecosystems through the E4T-project	Inspirational material e.g CLUSTER-meeting 2017: key note speakers, workshops, available on CLUSTER and E4T project web pages
Sharing best practices	Learning to work in different ecosystems through pilot program, enhancing student European/Global citizenship	Experience exchange workshop(s) for entrepreneurship teachers within E4T-project	Integrated pedagogical & entrepreneurial support for teachers & courses video material on CLUSTER and E4T project webpage
Making available	Financial support (E4T project) to access European/Global entrepreneurship education	Contacts and possibility in the future to visit different project partners' entrepreneurial ecosystems	Documented experiences on teaching in entrepreneurial ecosystems; how to integrate entrepreneurship into engineering education

Making the above actions visible will allow us to also increase the awareness of deans and university leadership of the needs and the challenges of integration of entrepreneurship education into engineering education, which is not the same as purely offering entrepreneurial courses or programs. Rather, this requires more extensive and targeted multidisciplinary approaches and possibly also changes in curricular structures. Moreover, through this study we also aim to create societal impact by influencing the mindset of our future graduates to become active contributors to the wellbeing of society through an innovative capacity and ability to present new solutions to global challenges. In order to achieve such goals it is important to offer our students the possibility to visit, learn and collaborate with students and teachers from other entrepreneurial ecosystems across Universities in Europe.

Concrete outputs from the above actions (Table 1.) are:

- information on engineering education which integrates entrepreneurship in different formats in our ecosystems
- visibility of accelerators to students who wish to pursue entrepreneurial activities in different European University systems
- possibilities for students and staff to visit and experience inspirational spaces in our ecosystems
- support for teachers to integrate entrepreneurship in teaching

Dissemination of the activities has been carried out as part of the CLUSTER network actions during 2017 and the work will continue as the study proceeds. Namely, the Vision, Mission and Values of the CLUSTER network have focused on Entrepreneurship Education as one of the key actions of the network (www.cluster.org). The topic for the CLUSTER symposium in November of 2017 focused on Entrepreneurship in Engineering Education (<http://cluster2017.aalto.fi/en/>). In order to make the contribution of the symposium visible to the target audience of the E4T project, all presentations of the symposium were recorded on videos and can be accessed through the CLUSTER

webpages. Work on the video – materials in ongoing, and the aim is to create a repository for teaching materials for teachers to access and share. Moreover, distributing information through other media is also under consideration. The CLUSTER symposium panelists included leading presenters in the areas of entrepreneurship education (<http://cluster2017.aalto.fi/en/videos/>) and all sessions of the symposium were delivered as hands-on pedagogical workshops for teachers to share Best Practices in integration of entrepreneurship into engineering education.

4. NEXT ACTIVITIES

One of the main outputs of E4T is the creation and piloting of a specific course on international entrepreneurship aiming at joining forces and offering a mobility scheme to Master students in their final year and to graduates currently enrolled in one of the courses offered by the partner universities to spend a short period at one of the other institutions in order to get exposure to a different ecosystem and specific elements and approaches not available at the home university. The combination of the seven ecosystems, their specificities and the courses/modules offered will be presented as a single product with joint marketing efforts, joint recruitment, joint selection and mutual recognition. This activity will both strengthen the single ecosystems and enhance their visibility on European scale. Indeed, entrepreneurial mobility literature (Filatotchev et al., 2011) show that returnee entrepreneurs can create a significant spillover effect that promotes innovation in other local high-tech firms in the home country of the returnee. Indeed, international commercial expertise and an international reputation open up possibilities for improving the drivers of internationalizing new ventures or newly created global ventures. However, Siegel & Wright (2015) show there is a lack of evidence on the benefits to host country universities that may arise from collaborations with students interested in entrepreneurship who return home. E4T can help to better understand these benefits.

As part of the dissemination activities, the E4T project will be concluded by an “Entrepreneurship Olympics” event in 2020. The plan is that students who have participated in the piloting of the E4T program in the different ecosystems of the partner universities, will present their projects at this event. Stakeholders from industry (including start-ups and established companies), academia and society will be invited to attend and contribute to taking the most promising projects further.